

ETHNIC COMPOSITION OF SURKHAN OASIS IN BUKHARA EMIRATE

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Annotation: In this article, the ethnic history of the Bekliks of the Surkhan oasis in the Bukhara Emirate, the ethnic composition of the population, social lifestyle, occupations, the entry of clans into the Beklik territories, the history of customs and some national traditions.

Key words: Emirate of Bukhara, ethnic history of Surkhan oasis, Denov province, population, entry of clans and peoples into the territory of the provinces, population.

The ethnic history of the Surkhan Bekli has been relatively little studied, and no extensive research has been conducted on the ethnic composition and social lifestyle of the population living in this area.

Turkic Qarluqs mainly lived in Togchiyan, Dashnabad, Sufiyan and other villages of Denov, Sariosia, Shorchi districts. Qarluqs are more common in Togchiyan, which is considered one of the mountainous villages. The Qarluqs settled in Shorchi and Saryosia regions in the middle of the 18th century. In some studies, it is said that there were more than 500 Karaguk families in Saryasia.

Turk-kaltatoyi clan was the majority in Kenagas guzar of Denov district. Residents belonging to the Kaltatoy clan also lived in Sarijoi and Yurchi districts. Also, the Kaltatoys lived in the village of Akkorgon in Sherabad and in the lower reaches of the Sangardak and Obizarang rivers, in the villages of Chontash, Shayton-kisloq, Jonbakhti, Jarkishloq, Karashiq, Telpakchinor and Kultepa (most of these villages are located in the territory of the present Uzun district).

Turko-barlos made up the majority of the population in the village of Namuna in the present Uzun district. Also, the Barlos lived in the village of Dashnabad mixed with the Chigatoys, in the west, in the villages of Shonsoi and Sangardak, near the Hazorbog canal, and in the east, in the villages of Chimtepa. At the beginning of the 16th century, the settlement of the Barlos in the Sariosia and Uzun districts of the present Surkhandarya region can be connected with the mass migration of the Uzbek clans to Central Asia under the leadership of Muhammad Shaibanikhan. At that time, they had certain privileges (for example, they were not hired as laborers) in the

Saryosiya estate. Even when the barlos come to visit, they are served a side of mutton. In addition to the Dashnabad village of Sariosiya, they also lived in Kudukdi, Qarabandi, and Shokqishlag. The fact that the Barlos came to Denov, Uzun, and Sariosia 350-400 years ago was shown separately in later studies.

It can be observed that the seeds of the forest are spread over a wide area in the oasis. The majority of the inhabitants of the village of Hajigi, located in the Sherabad oasis, on the right tributary of the Sherabad river, were doctors. It was found that there are 7,979 people from the forests in Hisar and Surkhan oases, and 2,400 people in Qabadian and its surroundings. Depending on their place of residence, they are divided into two groups - Hisori and Qabadion. They also lived in many villages in the middle and lower reaches of the Kafirkhan oasis, in the northern part of Bobotog. A part of Dorman's seed is also distributed in Sariosia and Denov regions. They were also found in the villages of Kholchayan, Faizovo, Serkharakat and the mountainous villages of Jiydabulok, Anorbulok and Pistamozor. According to the data, they came to the oasis 200-250 years ago. The coming of Great Medicines to the oasis is also associated with Muhammad Shaibani Khan. Abulghozi Bahadir Khan states that the origin of the Dorman clan is spread from the four sons of the Mongolian horse king Bichankayan. Before Bichankayan left the world, he made a will to elect his youngest son to the nation. Taking into account his father's will, they elect his younger son as khagan. But his four brothers were dissatisfied with the fact that their youngest brother was the chief, and when they appealed to the people to elect one of us as khagan, their wishes were rejected. As a result, four brothers move to a foreign land. In foreign countries, they are called "Dormon". Hafiz Tanish Bukhari in his work "Abdullanama" gives the following information about the dormon seed. "This category also spread from Norin. They say that these are brothers and four sons. They wanted to enter Genghis Khan's province from where they were, and they sat on him and entered his province. They say that the Dorman people are descendants of them, and the Mongolian word "dorman" means "four". In both sources, it is stated that the word "dorman" means "four" in Mongolian. From this it becomes clear that the descendants of the four young men were called "Dormans". According to the information, drugs consist of four categories and are divided into 18 clans. The first category of drugs is called ushuri. Seeds of this category: tibir, soltiq, karatona, kunur, ola-toy, jomontoy, okcha, yuli, etc. Seeds of the Kiyannoma category: qiyat, qabla, kutuchi, jertebar, tokizalu, white sheep. Seeds of the Gurdak category: Nogui, Kozak, Borboy, Usta. The clans of the Soxan category are not known. It was also noted that the herbs are divided into a number of varieties, such as

uvok, three seeds, blue bucket, thick, moon-marked, and sheep. In addition to the seeds mentioned above, we can observe that there are a number of other seeds. For example, among the trees living in the village of Serharakat in Uzun district, together with the seeds we have shown, there are seeds such as cucumber, mayda-turk, kosakalas, chorchur, jumuk, moda, kal, ogyo, borlok. can be found. In the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, the Dorman clan lived in separate villages, and in some villages they lived mixed with other Uzbek clans. Their location in the villages is divided according to the categories indicated above. In the socio-political life of the country and in the state administration, the influence of the forest seed was high. For example, during the time of Muhammad Shaibani Khan, it is recognized that the governor of the city of Kunduz was Dorman Urusbek. The Dorman clan maintained its high position in the social and political life of the country even during the rule of the Ashtarkhanids. They also actively participated in the social and political life of Bukhara Emirate. The main agricultural activity of the residents of the oasis was farming and animal husbandry. They engaged in farming in the plain part of the oasis and grew wheat, barley, rice, cotton, policing, horticulture and other agricultural products.

On the mountain slopes and hills, they engaged in dry farming and cattle breeding, and in cattle breeding, along with horned animals, they were more engaged in sheep breeding. The Hisor, that is, the humped type of sheep, was raised more often. At the beginning of the 19th and 20th centuries, the Dorman clan lived in certain villages of the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, but now we can see that they live in all districts of the oasis. For example, in Uzun district, it was observed that Dorman clan used to live in three to four villages, but now the number of villages in which they live is more than 15. If we think about the clans living in the oasis, we will see that they are divided into many small clans. Among them are such as a single bell and a caraway seed.

The Harduris spoke the Tajik language. Most of them lived in the villages of the Machai river basin. More than 350 farms of Harduris are registered in the villages of Khojand and Upper Machai. They lived here together with the Turks. These village harduris gradually switched to Uzbek language and called themselves Uzbek harduris (they lived mixed with Uzbek chigatoys). Around Boisun is the village of Harduri, whose inhabitants believe that they originated from Boshcharvok, which is located in the upper reaches of Kichik Oradaryo near Machai. It was also determined that they lived in the village of Tarakli (today Tarakhil) of Denov. This village is also known as Harduri village. In Darband, the number of Harduris, who are considered the third

clan after the Tajik Chigatoys and Kungirats, was not very large, and they lived in separate villages located far from each other. Russian military colonel Belyaevsky told them: "From the outside, they are not rich, they live in low, simple houses. "Harduris also marry Tajiks and Khungirats," he explains.

Representatives of the Kenagas clan were not very numerous, but mainly lived in Denov, in the villages of Tortuvli and Gazarak in the Sarijoi estate. The Mangits, considered one of the Uzbek clans, were a minority in Eastern Bukhara. They lived in the villages of Azan, Manguzar and Khojagi of Sherabad province. Representatives of the Khintai clan of Uzbeks lived mixed with Turkmens in two villages of Sherabad province: Poshkhurd and China, as well as in the village of Chinaan near the city of Denov. According to information, the Kovchin clan lived scattered in the villages near the city of Denov, in the suburbs of Boysun, and in the villages of Sayrob. They came to Surkhandarya from Kashkadarya oasis.

It was determined that the population belonging to the Jaloyir clan is located on the right bank of the Surkhan River, south of Shorchi, in the village of Jaloyir, which is named after the clan.

The Lakai clan is mainly located in Vakht, Kolob, Kurgantepa of the present Republic of Tajikistan. Lived in Hisar and other settlements. B. Kh. Karmisheva did not provide information about their presence in the Surkhan oasis in his research. N. Norboyev's research mentions the existence of a small number of lackeys in the Zharkurgan, Kumkurgan districts and the city of Termiz of the Surkhan oasis.

It is known that the Karatamgali clan settled mainly in villages around Sariosia and Uzun. In addition to Uzbeks and Tajiks, representatives of several other nationalities lived in the oasis.

It was found that the representatives of the Iranian people in the oasis were not very numerous, they were scattered in the villages of Karluq and Kichik Vakhshuvor of the Denov province, and Karabagh of the Boysun province. Gypsies were the majority in the northern part of the oasis. In 1924, 1418 Gypsies were registered only in Sariosia and Yurchi. In the northern part of the Surkhan oasis, there are more than 100 of their farms, where more than 1000 people live. Gypsies, in their turn, are divided into groups of clans: kabi, sagbozi, kogani, chigatoy, bori, slave or ghulam. Sagbozi and Kokani lived in Saryasia. There are opinions that Afghans came to South Uzbekistan and Tajikistan from Afghanistan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Small groups of them lived in villages, more than 300 families of Afghans were found in the oasis. In 1949, as a result of surveys and research conducted by B. Karmisheva, it was determined that there were 17 Afghan villages in the areas of

Kolob and Sherabad districts. Afghans lived mixed with Uzbeks and Tajiks in 6 villages in Saryasia, Uzbeks and Tajiks in 2 villages in Denov, and Uzbeks in 4 villages in Sherabad District. Smaller groups of Afghans are more common in villages around major cities and markets.

Indians also formed a minority in the oasis. They lived in cities and large villages near the market and were mainly engaged in trade and entrepreneurship (usury). They lived only in Yurchi as a family.

Turkmens are mainly located in Sherabad district. 3,825 Turkmans were registered on the banks of the Amudarya and in Termiz district, of which 1,190 were Saruk, 1,015 were Esari, and 1,620 were Shikhs. Turkmens lived in their own villages. It was determined that there were 12 Turkmen villages in the oasis, and they lived together with Uzbek Chigatai only in the village of Joyjanganal. According to Captain Vasiliev's statistics, there was a large clan of Turkmen along the banks of the Amudarya, and their number was about 4,000. At the end of the 19th century, 36 Jewish families were registered in Boisun, which consisted of merchant families. One of the big merchants in Boisun Bek, the son of Su Yun Pinhas, a Jew, had more than 500 hectares of land and about 14 shops in the city. Lt. Col. Galkin writes that in Pattakesar (Termiz) there are also Jews among other inhabitants. After the Russian Empire subjugated the Bukhara Emirate, Russian citizens began to settle in the territories of the Bukhara Emirate, as in other places in Central Asia. At first, they were formed by the military, businessmen and merchants. By the end of the 19th century, the number of Russians increased significantly as a result of the development of trade relations between Russia and Bukhara, on the one hand, and the arrival of Russian border troops. For example, in 1883, the 14th Turkestan battalion arrived in Karki, and by 1886, a part of reinforced Russian troops arrived. In the same year, Russian troops were deployed to Chorjoi. According to the Russia-Bukhara Treaty of January 15, 1883, the territories of Pattakesar and Salihabad located around Termiz were given to the Russians. After that, Russian military units belonging to the 7th border district began to settle here. According to the data, by 1900, 8052 men and 2069 women lived in the village of Pattakesar, where the Russians lived. The main part of this population was made up of the Russian military. Armenians, Tatars and representatives of other nationalities lived here together with them. Based on the study of the ethnic composition of the population of South Uzbekistan in the early 19th-20th centuries, the following conclusions can be drawn: the Uzbek and Tajik populations have been living in the oasis since ancient times, engaged in agriculture, animal husbandry, handicrafts and trade. At the beginning of the 19th and 20th

centuries, the inhabitants of the Surkhan oasis had a complex ethnic composition, among them there were also clans that did not mix with the settled population and preserved the Uzbek clan-class system.

They have preserved their own way of life, customs, culture and some ethnic characteristics; The history of the Uzbek clans, who still live in the region and make up the majority, is mainly connected with the entry of Muhammad Shaibani Khan into Central Asia at the beginning of the 16th century. They are spread not only in separate areas, but in many cases throughout the villages and guzars where local clans (who lived here before) live; The location of many clans of the Uzbek people in the Surkhan oasis shows that there is a significant difference, although not sharp, between the northern and southern regions. Although Uzbeks live in the plain part of the oasis, and Tajiks live in the mountainous areas, they form the basis of the population, but many other nationalities also live there.

Therefore, the Surkhan Bekliks can be included in the regions with a multi-ethnic population at the beginning of the 19th and 20th centuries. Some inaccuracies and confusions are evident in the information about the history, location and number of people living in the Bukhara Emirate and the oasis. So, generations of representatives of different nationalities are living in harmony and tolerance in all areas of the oasis, and with the expansion of population and living areas, customs and traditions that have been formed since ancient times live side by side here. has an effective influence on mutual cooperation and further rapprochement of representatives of different nationalities.

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